

IMMERSIVE LEARNING EXPERIENCES THROUGH THE USE OF VIRTUAL REALITY IN ESP METHODOLOGY

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In English for Specific Purposes (ESP) education, virtual reality (VR) is being implemented extensively to create immersive, contextualized learning experiences. A major change in how students interact with content has been brought about by the incorporation of Virtual Reality (VR) technology into the classroom. Virtual reality (VR) provides a platform for practicing language skills in authentic and professional settings, especially in ESP, where students study for specialized fields. Moreover, virtual reality (VR) facilitates vocabulary learning, student engagement, and the development of practical skills by modeling professional settings.

Theoretical Foundations

VR in educational setting is consistent with experiential learning theory, which promotes deeper learning through active engagement in meaningful situations. Kolb (1984) asserted that learning is most successful when students are able to put their theoretical knowledge to use in real world situations. Such experiential learning is made possible by VR's immersive surroundings, which are especially helpful in ESP where real-world applications are crucial [1].

Virtual reality applications in ESP

1. Acquisition of vocabulary

VR has shown promise in assisting ESP learners in understanding and remembering specialized terminology. One of the appropriate examples of using a VR-based method is English for Geography course in which students were taught vocabulary using VR-based method. Compared to conventional video-based approaches, students' vocabulary learning and engagement levels were higher when they indulged in immersing simulations, such as studying the hydrologic cycle [2].

2. Nursing Education and Healthcare

VR also allows nursing students to practice using medical terminology and dealing with patients in realistic settings. In a research study with nursing students of Chinese college, Wu et al. (2023) discovered that virtual reality (VR) improved their capacity to combine language proficiency with real-world information, making classes more interesting and productive [3].

3. ESP terminology via the Metaverse

Christoforou (2022) emphasized how the metaverse language learning program IMMERSE can be utilized in ESP instruction. The platform allowed students to practice language skills relevant to their areas and encounter contextualized situations by imitating authentic professional settings. Examples of these scenarios included conducting online meetings and performing tasks together in virtual (realistic) workplaces [4].

4. Presentation and Public Speaking Proficiencies

Additionally, VR offers a perfect setting for honing public speaking, which is an essential ability in many ESP context. By enabling students to practice presentations in monitored, authentic environments, virtual reality's immersive qualities help lower nervousness [4].

Virtual reality bridges the gap between classroom education and real-world application, providing ESP learners with previously unattainable opportunities. In addition to

improving language proficiency, virtual reality (VR) helps students get ready for the demands of their professional settings by facilitating comprehensive and contextualized learning experiences.

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